

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

METHOD DEVELOPMENT AND VALIDATION OF SIMULTANEOUS ESTIMATION OF AZITHROMYCIN AND DEXAMETHASONE IN EYE DROPS BY RP-HPLC

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 19/11/2018
Available online
001/2019

Keywords

Azithromycin (Azasite) and
Dexamethasone Sodium
Phosphate (Decadron),
Analytical Method
Development,
Validation,
Ayzeecon-D,
RP-HPLC.

ABSTRACT

A simple, reversed phase high performance liquid chromatography (RP-HPLC) method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone in their combined formulation from the eye drop. The GRACE ODS C18, 250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m, L1 packing, column was maintained at an ambient temperature and 230 nm λ max conditions. The mixture of Methanol and 0.0335M Phosphate Buffer (pH 7.5) in the ratio of (80:20 v/v) mobile phase was used in the flow rate of 1.2 ml/min. Azithromycin and Dexamethasone peaks were eluted at 3.832 min and 4.798 min respectively with good resolution. The above method was validated in terms of System suitability, linearity, accuracy, precision, Limit of Detection (LOD), Limit of Quantification (LOQ) in accordance with ICH guidelines. The results obtained from the method validation were within the acceptable limit. In conclusion a method has been developed for the simultaneous estimation of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone in combined dosage form. The linearity range of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone were found to be from 0.1-12 μ g/ml for Azithromycin, 0.1-8 μ g/ml for Dexamethasone. Linear regression coefficients were found to be 0.9931 and 0.9949 for Azithromycin and Dexamethasone respectively.

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Please cite this article in press as **Chandrakanth Bandapally** et al. ADR Assessment Methods: an Overview. Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research.2018:8(12).

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INTRODUCTION

Azithromycin is a bacteriostatic drug acts by inhibiting protein synthesis. It binds to 50S ribosomal subunits of the 70S bacterial ribosomes, and therefore inhibits RNA-dependent protein synthesis in bacterial cells. Azithromycin interferes with transpeptidation and translocation thus there is inhibition of protein synthesis and hence inhibition of cell growth. It is used to treat certain eye infections. It is a macrolides antibiotic that works by stopping the growth of bacteria. Its effects may be bacteriostatic or bactericidal depending of the organism and the drug concentration. Its long half life, which enables once daily dosing and shorter administration durations, is a property distinct from other macrolides. A semi synthetic antibiotic belonging to the macrolides subgroup of azalides is used to treat STDs due to Chlamydia and gonorrhea, community-acquired pneumonia, pelvic inflammatory disease, pediatric otitis media and pharyngitis, and Mycobacterium avium complex (MAC) in patients with advanced HIV disease. its having structure similarities to erythromycin but azithromycin reaches higher intracellular concentrations than erythromycin, increasing its efficacy and duration of action^[1,4].

Fig.1. Structure of Azithromycin.

Dexamethasone is a steroid that prevents the release of substances in the body that causes inflammation. It is a glucocorticoid agonist. Unbound Dexamethasone crosses cell membranes and binds with high affinity to specific cytoplasmic glucocorticoid receptors. This complex binds to DNA elements (glucocorticoid response elements) which results in a modification of transcription and hence protein synthesis in order to achieve inhibition of leukocyte infiltration at the site of inflammation, interference in the function of mediators of inflammatory response, suppression of humoral immune responses, and reduction in edema or scar tissue. The anti-inflammatory actions of Dexamethasone are thought to involve phospholipase A₂ inhibitory proteins, lipocortins, which control the biosynthesis of potent mediators of inflammation such as prostaglandins and leukotrienes. Dexamethasone eye drops are used to treat short term inflammatory eye conditions .They contain a corticosteroid which helps to relieve inflammation, redness and irritation^[2,4].

Fig.2. Structure of Dexamethasone.

Both the drugs are marketed as combined dose Eye drops formulation in the ratio of 10:1 mg Ayzeecon-D. Literature survey revealed that there are some methods reported for the simultaneous & individual estimation of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone^[5,6], by using UV-spectrophotometer^[7], and RP-HPLC^[8-11]. HPLC method is more sensitive method to detect samples at low concentration with accuracy than UV-Visible spectrophotometer. Therefore, updated & challenged methods are required for the simultaneous estimation of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone. So the proposed method provides fast separation with effective resolution, good peak shape, use of lesser sample volumes and buffer volumes, providing cost effective. The proposed established method was validated with respect to specificity, linearity, precision, accuracy, Limit of detection and Limit of quantification subject to ICH Q2B guidelines 1996 and Q2 (R1) guidelines 2005^[12-13].

OBJECTIVE:

The Present study was aimed to develop simple, rapid, greater sensitive analytical method for faster elution by using RP-HPLC for the simultaneous estimation of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Methanol (HPLC grade) was obtained from Merck specialties private limited, Mumbai, India. Acetonitrile (HPLC grade) was obtained from Merck specialties private limited, Mumbai, India and Potassium di hydrogen Phosphate. Pure drugs of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone were obtained as gift samples. Ayzeecon-D Eye drops manufactured by Indiana ophthalmic purchased from pharmacy is used for the analysis. The label claim states that this formulation contains 10mg of Azithromycin and 1mg of Dexamethasone of each eye drops.

Instrumentation and chromatographic condition

HPLC method development and validation were done on SHIMADZU (Japan) liquid chromatography equipped with LC-10AD pump, SPD-10A UV/Vis detector and Rheodyne 7725i injection with a 20 μ L loop. For instrument control, data acquisition and processing, the chromatographic system was interfaced to empower N-2000 solutions software. Other instruments included are Contech Electronic balance CAS-44, Citizen-Digital ultrasonic cleaner.

The column used for chromatographic separations was reverse phase GRACE ODS C18, 250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m column, the analytical wave length was given as 214 nm and samples of 20 μ L were injected.

METHOD DEVELOPMENT**Preparation of mobile phase**

The chromatographic separations were accomplished using mobile phase consisting of Methanol: Phosphate buffer (80:20 % v/v), filtered through 0.45 μ m filter using vacuum pump and degassed in fast clean ultrasonic cleaner. Mobile phase was pumped in isocratic mode at a flow rate of 1 ml/min at room temperature.

Preparation of standard solutions

Stock solution was prepared by dissolving 10mg of Azithromycin and 1mg of Dexamethasone in 10 ml of methanol: Phosphate buffer (80:20 % v/v). This was 1000 μ g/ml solution.

Fig.3. Chromatogram of standard solution (10 μ g/ml Azithromycin and 10 μ g/ml Dexamethasone).

Preparation of working standard solutions

From above solution 0.1 ml was taken into 10ml of volumetric flask. The volume was made up to the mark with methanol: Phosphate buffer (80:20 % v/v) mixer. The concentration of each drug in solution was 10 μ g/ml.

Preparation of sample solutions for assay:

Ayzeecon-D each containing 10 mg of azithromycin and 1 mg of Dexamethasone solution taken and extracted in to methanol: Phosphate buffer (80:20 % v/v) mixer, and filtered. 1 ml from filtrate was taken in to 10ml volumetric flask; volume was made up to mark with diluents. The 0.1 ml from above filtrate pipetted out into a 10 ml of volumetric flask, volume was made up to mark with mobile phase. The resulted solution was sonicated for 10minutes and injected.

METHOD VALIDATION

The developed method was validated for linearity, Range, Precision, Accuracy, LOD and LOQ as per the ICH guidelines.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Method Development

For the RP-HPLC, chromatographic conditions were optimized to get a best resolution and peak shape. The selection of mobile phase was based on peak parameters like symmetry, theoretical plates and capacity factor. Symmetrical peaks with good separation (retention time for Azithromycin and Dexamethasone were found to be 3.832 min and 4.798 min) were obtained with reverse phase GRACE ODS C18, 250 x 4.6 mm, 5 μ m column. The mobile phase containing Methanol: Phosphate buffer (75:25 % v/v) was used at a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The optimum wavelength for detection and quantification was at 230 nm λ max, at which good detector response was obtained for both. The results are given in the following Table 1.

Method Validation:

The proposed method was validated as per International Conference on Harmonization (ICH) guidelines.

Linearity and Range

Linearity was established by least squares linear regression analysis of the calibration curve. The calibration curves were linear over the concentration range of 0.1-12 μ g/ml for Azithromycin, 0.1-8 μ g/ml for Dexamethasone. Peak areas were plotted versus respective concentrations and linear regression analysis was performed on the resultant curves. Correlation coefficients were found to be 0.9931 and 0.9949 for Azithromycin and Dexamethasone respectively. Calibration graph of Azithromycin, and Dexamethasone by RP-HPLC was shown in the following Fig.4 and Fig.5. The results are given in Table 1.

Linearity of Azithromycin.

S.NO	CONCENTRATION (PPM)	PEAK AREA
1	0.1	2545
2	0.2	6542
3	0.4	12568
4	0.8	30254
5	1	48569
6	2	88456
7	4	171759
8	8	336584
9	10	365894
10	12	401524

Fig.4. Calibration graph of Azithromycin by RP-HPLC.

Linearity of Dexamethasone.

S.NO	Concentration (ppm)	Peak area
1	0.1	13563
2	0.2	13584
3	0.4	13695
4	0.8	13999
5	1	14562
6	2	16587
7	4	19546
8	8	27550

Fig.5. Calibration graph of Dexamethasone by RP-HPLC.

Precision

The precision of the analytical method was studied by multiple sampling of the homogenous sample. The precision was done at two levels (intraday and inter day). Intraday precision was done by analyzing the intermediate concentration of each drugs (4 µg/ml Azithromycin and 4 µg/ml Dexamethasone) for six times. Inter day precision was also measured over three consecutive days for the same drug concentrations for six times. The %RSD values were calculated for each of them and the low RSD values indicated that the method is precise. The results were found within in the acceptable criteria of %RSD NMT 2.The results are given in Table 1.

S.NO	Azithromycin	Dexamethasone
1	16587	171759
2	16496	170679
3	16507	170896
4	16579	16978
5	16580	170796
6	16591	171268
Average :	16556.67	170846
SDV:	43.10298	694.0844
% RSD:	0.260	0.404

Accuracy

Recovery studies were carried out by applying the method to drug sample to which known amount of standard Azithromycin and Dexamethasone corresponding to 80, 100 and 120 % of label claim had been added. At each level of the amount three determinations were performed. The % recovery found within the acceptable criteria (98-102%). The results are given in Table 1.

ACCURACY LEVEL	STANDARD	TEST	SPICKED	% RECOVERY
AZITHROMYCIN 50%	16587	14562	31118	102 %
	16496	14463	30988	
	16507	14369	31897	
AVERAGE :	16530	14464.67	31334.56	
SDV:	49.669	96.51079	491.4525	
%RSD:	0.300	0.666	1.568	

ACCURACY LEVEL	STANDARD	TEST	SPICKED	% RECOVERY
AZITHROMYCIN 100%	18987	14562	33356	99.8%
	18890	14463	33298	
	18798	14369	33348	
AVERAGE :	18891.67	14464.67	33334	
SDV:	94.511	96.51079	31.432	
%RSD:	0.500	0.666	0.094	

ACCURACY LEVEL	STANDARD	TEST	SPICKED	% RECOVERY
AZITHROMYCIN 150%	20989	14562	35395	99.3%
	20908	14463	35401	
	20896	14369	34989	
AVERAGE :	20931	14464.67	35261	
SDV:	50.589	96.51079	236.155	
%RSD:	0.241	0.666	0.669	

ACCURACY LEVEL	STANDARD	TEST	SPICKED	% RECOVERY
DEXAMETHASONE 50%	171759	365894	533400	99.6%
	170679	360986	532906	
	170896	359989	531962	
AVERAGE :	171111.3	362289.7	532756	
SDV:	571.2963	3160.998	730.6408	
%RSD:	0.338	0.872	0.137	

ACCURACY LEVEL	STANDARD	TEST	SPICKED	% RECOVERY
DEXAMETHASONE 100%	201897	365894	564199	100.3%
	201818	360986	564098	
	202212	359989	565175	
AVERAGE :	201909	362289.7	564490.7	
SDV:	97.555	3160.998	594.797	
%RSD:	0.048	0.872	0.105	

ACCURACY LEVEL	STANDARD	TEST	SPICKED	% RECOVERY
DEXAMETHASONE 150%	269866	365894	630287	100.2 %
	265468	360986	631254	
	268658	359989	630989	
AVERAGE :	267997	362289.7	630843	
SDV:	2272.215	3160.998	499.686	
%RSD:	0.847	0.872	0.079	

Sensitivity:

LOD and LOQ decide the sensitivity of the method. LOD is the lowest detectable concentration of the analyte by the method while LOQ is the minimum quantifiable concentration. LOD and LOQ were calculated by standard calibration curves. The results are given in Table 1.

System suitability studies:

System suitability parameters like number of theoretical plates (N) (NLT 2000), peak asymmetry factor (As), tailing factor (NMT 2), and resolution (NLT 2) were studied. The results are given in the table.

S. no	Theoretical plates	Tailing factor	Resolution	Asymmetry	Retention time
Azithromycin	2658	1.4	2.6	1.2	3.83
Dexamethasone	2965	0.8	2.9	1.5	4.79

Table 1: Summary of validation parameters.

Parameters	Azithromycin	Dexamethasone
Linearity range ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	0.1-12	0.1-8
Correlation coefficient	0.9931	0.9949
Slope	36088	1786
Intercept	7610	12951
LOD ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	1.60	0.88
LOQ ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	4.84	2.67
Recovery %		
50%		
Recovery % \pm SD	102%	99.6%
100%	99.8%	100.3%
Recovery % \pm SD		
120%	99.3%	100.2%
Recovery % \pm SD	0.653	
Precision	100.3% \pm 0.08	
Intraday (n=6) (%RSD)		0.388
SD	0.293	562.10
Inter day (n=6) (%RSD)	108.26	0.375
SD	0.272	543.26
Theoretical plates	100.58	3027.1
Tailing factor	2488.7	1.778
Resolution	0.876	
	5.502	

*RSD and SD denote relative standard deviation and standard deviation.

Analysis of marketed formulation:

The proposed procedures were successfully applied for the simultaneous estimation of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone in the formulation and the drug contents in each sample were calculated by comparison with the appropriate standard solution of the drug. The results obtained were in agreement with label claim. The results of analysis are given in (Table 2) (Fig. 6).

Table no 2. Analysis of marketed formulation.

Drug	Labeled	Amount		
	Amount (mg)	Found (mg)	% Assay	% RSD
Azithromycin	10	12.498	102	0.66
Dexamethasone	0.1	0.0967	99.6	0.87

*Mean of three observations.

Fig.6. Chromatogram of formulation (2.5 µg/ml Azithromycin and 25 µg/ml Dexamethasone).

CONCLUSION

On the basis of my experimental results, the proposed method is suitable for the quantitative determination of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone in eye drop. The method provides great sensitivity, adequate linearity and repeatability.

The estimation of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone was done by RP-HPLC. The Phosphate buffer was pH 7.5 and the mobile phase was optimized which consists of Methanol: Phosphate buffer mixed in the ratio of 80:20 % v/v. The GRACE ODS C18, 250 x 4.6 mm, 5 µm, L1 packing column used as stationary phase. The detection was carried out using UV detector at 230 nm. The solutions were chromatographed at a constant flow rate of 1.2 ml/min. the linearity range of Azithromycin and Dexamethasone were found to be from 0.1-12µg/ml for Azithromycin, 0.1-8µg/ml for Dexamethasone. Linear regression coefficients were found to be 0.9931 and 0.9949 for Azithromycin and Dexamethasone respectively. Azithromycin and Dexamethasone peaks were eluted at 3.832 min and 4.798 min respectively with good resolution. High percentage of recovery was observed and the method is free from the interference of excipients used in the formulation. So the method can be useful in the routine quality control of these drugs.

RECOMMENDED FUTURE RESEARCH:

Future research is recommended on Azithromycin and Dexamethasone combinational simultaneous estimation from any pharmaceutical dosage form.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

I am very grateful thanks to Aurobindo College of pharmaceutical sciences, Warangal, for giving a support to complete my work in college premises.

LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

MeOH	:	Methanol
CC	:	Chiral Chromatography
CAM	:	Complementary and alternative medicine
CEC	:	Cation Exchange Chromatography
DAD	:	Diode Array Detector
FDA	:	Food and Drug Administration
G.R	:	Gradient Reagent
HETP	:	Height Equivalent Theoretical Plates
HPLC	:	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
IR	:	Infra Red
ICH	:	International Conference on Harmonization
LC	:	Liquid chromatography
LOD	:	Limit of Detection
LOQ	:	Limit of Quantification
ODS COLUMN	:	Octadecylsilyl groups
RNA	:	Ribonucleic Acid
DNA	:	Deoxyribonucleic
HIV	:	Human Immunodeficiency virus
µg	:	Microgram
mg	:	Milligram
HPLC	:	High Performance Liquid Chromatography
nm	:	Nanometres
µL	:	Micro liters
µgm	:	Micro gram
NMT	:	Not more than
NLT	:	Not less than
No	:	Number
PMT	:	Photo Multiplier Tube
PDA	:	Photo Diode Array
ppm	:	Parts per million
pKa	:	Dissociation constant
pH	:	Negative logarithm of hydrogen ion concentration
RP-HPLC	:	Reversed Phase High Performance Liquid Chromatography
RPC	:	Reversed Phase Chromatography
R _s	:	Resolution
R _f	:	Retention factor
r ²	:	Correlation coefficient
R _t	:	Retention time
SEC	:	Size Exchange Chromatography
Std	:	Standard
SDV	:	Standard Deviation Value
T	:	Tailing factor
UV	:	Ultra Violet
Vis	:	Visible
WHO	:	World Health Organisation
%RSD	:	Percentage Relative Standard Deviation
λ _{max}	:	Maximum wavelength
ε ⁰	:	Solvent strength
Fig	:	Figure

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